

Electrical Reliability and Breakdown Mechanisms in Single-Walled Carbon Nanotubes*

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Abstract—We show that single-walled carbon nanotubes can carry current densities $> 1 \text{ MA/cm}^2$ for several hours but degrade over time at rates that depend on initial input power. Above a current threshold maximum, we observe large scale physical migration at the CNT-Au electrode interface, which results in Au voids as large as 300 nm in diameter and nearby mounds 3x as tall as the original 50 nm structure. We suggest that the likely mechanism for this void and mound growth is either localized melting, thermomigration, electromigration, or some combination of these. We also show two unique end-of-life breakdown mechanisms for CNTs, a classical fracture via resistive breakdown, and a physically intact but nonconducting failure mode.

I. INTRODUCTION

As the feature sizes of integrated circuits shrink below 45 nm, the performance and capabilities of very-large-scale integration schemes become increasingly limited by the interconnects that transport power, ground, and clock information to the various circuits of the chip. Present copper interconnect technology cannot supply the required current densities without suffering from electromigration and thermomechanical reliability issues. The recent 2009 International Technology Roadmap for Semiconductors (ITRS) [1] suggested that electrically contacted bundles of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) [2] may replace copper at these small length scales because of their high current-carrying capacities, heightened thermal conductivity, and enhanced resistance to electromigration.

Several groups have demonstrated that densely packed *bundles* of single-walled (SW) CNTs have the greatest potential for reducing overall interconnect resistance and delay-causing capacitive loading [3]. Most recent CNT-based interconnect work has focused on fabrication issues, such as lowering CNT-metal contact resistances [4] or integrating bundled CNT vias at low temperatures to be compatible with conventional complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor technology [5]. Despite these ongoing technological advancements, the electrical reliability of CNT-based interconnects has been largely overlooked, although they are known to be sensitive to material and process variability.

Only a few studies [6], [7] have investigated how CNTs will respond to large current densities over long time scales (minutes, hours, etc.) required in end-use applications. These studies have suggested that CNTs can endure large currents for long periods without damage accumulation [7], but additional validation via repeated experimentation is needed for a full

understanding. In this work, we have used dielectrophoretic self-assembly of CNTs to statistically investigate the reliability of several CNT interconnect devices. We show that CNTs can indeed sustain high current densities for long periods, but will slowly degrade when a constant current is applied. Despite the high current carrying capabilities of CNTs, we suggest that the metal electrodes at the CNT-metal electrode interface will fail in dramatic fashion due to either electromigration, thermomigration, or localized melting whenever high currents are applied above a specific threshold. This alarming result suggests that the reliability of CNTs must be considered as part of a composite system that includes the CNTs and their associated electrodes, in order to take advantage of the high current carrying capabilities of the CNTs. Finally, we demonstrate two distinct CNT failure mechanisms in CNTs that depend on the nature of electrical input.

II. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Several hundred Au/Ti (45 nm / 5 nm thick) electrode pad pairs with gaps ranging from 450 nm to 3 μm were assembled via conventional photolithographic techniques on a Si wafer with 3 μm of thermally grown SiO_2 . Initially, all left-right electrode pairs were connected in parallel, so they could be simultaneously biased during dielectrophoresis. Highly purified SWCNTs suspended in a solution of deionized water with ionic surfactants were further dispersed in ethanol, before being mass-assembled. Dielectrophoresis [8] involved application of a 5 V_{pp} AC signal across the electrodes for 1 min before removing the excess solution with air. SWCNTs were found to be well-adhered to both electrodes near their points of closest approach, where electric fields were strongest. Through scanning electron microscope (SEM) and atomic force microscope (AFM) images, we verified that the location and adhesion of these SWCNTs were unaffected by the subsequent high-speed spin-coat photoresist deposition and second photolithographic process used to separate the individual Au/Ti electrodes. The final individual metal-CNTs-metal interconnect devices, consisting of multiple parallel CNTs and CNT bundles, were then electrically tested in ambient atmosphere and found to have total initial resistances ranging from 0.5 k Ω - 10 k Ω , depending on gap size and number of self-assembled CNTs. Although the initial CNT solution contained 2/3 semiconducting and 1/3 metallic SWCNTs according to the supplier, the resulting devices behaved

Fig. 1. Dielectrophoretically assembled CNT-based interconnects can sustain large current for long periods of time, but all experience an initial increase in current up to a well-defined peak followed by a continuous degradation over time. The rate of these events seems correlated to input power at time $t = 0$. At high input powers (tests **D** and **E**) current increases can happen quickly and suddenly, but are always followed by a subsequent degradation of current.

ohmically at voltages < 1 V and showed only a small tunnel barrier at higher voltages. Several studies have suggested that dielectrophoretic assembly, by its nature, is likely to preferentially attract metallic CNTs while leaving semiconducting CNTs in solution [8].

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Figure 1 shows how currents in CNT-based interconnects typically varied when a DC voltage (V_h) was applied for several hours. Five CNT interconnects with similar starting resistances were exposed to a constant applied DC voltage ranging from 1 V - 1.8 V. In Figure 1, time $t = 0$ corresponds to the beginning of the voltage hold, although the voltage had been previously ramped from 0 V to V_h over the course of several minutes at a rate of 0.01 V/s (not shown). In each of these tests, we saw a steady increase in the current up to a peak value, followed by a slow continuous degradation over longer periods. While previous studies [9], [10] have demonstrated that current stressing and the accompanying localized Joule heating could reduce the CNT-electrode contact resistance and improve overall current flow in the device, such experiments were normally performed over the course of only a few seconds. None of these studies showed improved CNT-electrode contact behavior over several hours, as in Figure 1.

We find (see Figure 1 table insert) that the total time to peak current appears to be correlated to the input power (P_I) at the beginning of the voltage hold, where $P_I = V_h I(t = 0)$. The

Fig. 2. SEM images of CNT interconnect topography (a) initially and (b) after 1.8 V was applied for 1 h, showing Au recession. AFM height images in (c) two- and (d) three-dimensions of same interconnect show gold mounds 2-3 times as thick as the original structure.

high-input-power experiments (**D** and **E**), where an increase in current occurs almost immediately, may provide insight into the current progression at the lower input powers (**A**, **B**, **C**). Such an abrupt current spike was always accompanied by recession of parts of the gold electrode away from the gap at the CNT-Au interface, as shown by the SEM images in Figures 2(a) and (b). We observed a strong correlation between Au recession and the local density of CNTs, suggesting either an electrically or thermally activated migration at the CNT-Au interface. AFM topography scans obtained via low-force amplitude-modulated tapping mode (see Figures 2(c) and (d)), showed mounds of Au, typically two to three times as tall as the overall electrode, clumped around the recession areas.

We found such Au migration was observable only when a certain current threshold was reached, as demonstrated by Figure 3. In this “slow migration test,” the applied voltage was repeatedly increased by 0.01 V and held for 460 s while the applied current was captured every 1 s. Qualitatively, Figure 3(a) follows the same trend observed in the experiments of Figure 1, with an initial increase in current up to a peak value followed by a slow continuous degradation. However, Figure 3b shows that the current increases dramatically only when the applied voltage is ≥ 1.54 V. The next three subsequent holds at slightly higher voltages led to more drastic increases in current, with the largest spike in current occurring when the voltage was held at 1.57 V. The inset to Figure 3a shows the current progression near the peak, with each specific voltage-holds highlighted by either a thick black line or a thin red line.

Figure 4 emphasizes this minimum current threshold requirement with three unique CNT interconnect systems

Fig. 3. (a) Slow migration test showing the induced current measured every 1 s as the applied voltage increases by 0.01 V every 460 s. The inset in (a) is a magnified look at the current progression near the peak for specific held voltages (highlighted by alternating thick black and thin red lines). (b) Initially, the current increases very slowly until a threshold current of about 1.5 mA is reached.

that were electrically stressed by the same slow migration method used in Figure 3. The initial resistance of these three interconnects was very similar, suggesting that they contained nearly the same numbers of conducting CNTs. As the applied voltage was sequentially increased by 0.01 V and held, the instantaneous current at the beginning of the hold and the final current at the end of the hold were recorded. The total change in current for a given hold was then plotted against the instantaneous current. In all three devices, the change in current was minimal at low applied currents. However, when the total current through the CNT-interconnect reached 1.5 mA, the current increased rapidly, eventually reaching a peak value, then subsequently decreased during the degradation event. Through these examples and other experiments, we have found that the device must carry 1.5 mA - 2.0 mA of current for Au migration to be clearly visible in the SEM.

After reaching a peak in the current, we continued to ramp the voltage and observed that the current degradation would become increasingly less stable and more sporadic until it reached an open-circuit state (see Figure 5 for behavior after 40+ hours of testing). The SEM image of Figure 5(a) shows more pronounced Au migration and mounding on the grounded side of the circuit into which current flows. In addition to this migration, the CNT bundles appear to have darker contrast near the center of the gap. The higher-magnification images (see Figure 5b) show that the CNTs appear to be intact, which suggests that the regions showing darker contrast are

Fig. 4. The change in current in three similar CNT-interconnect devices plotted as a function of current at the beginning of each specific hold voltage for slow migration tests like that of Figure 3. The legend indicates how long each voltage was applied before increasing the voltage 0.01 V. The current threshold (≈ 1.5 mA) required for Au migration becomes clear.

likely caused by type I voltage contrast (VC) [11]. In type I VC, primary electrons from focused SEM beams can create localized potentials on the surface, which depend primarily on the local material's ability to dissipate those electrons. These surface potentials can affect the detection of low-energy SE1 electrons collected by the in-lens SEM detector like the one used to acquire the image in Figure 5. We can thus conclude that the darkened portions of the CNT bundles are more positively biased than the rest of the CNTs and Au electrodes, suggesting that there is some local discontinuity or defect that disrupts electron flow through the CNTs.

This nonconducting but physically intact CNT failure mode is unique and strikingly different from the well-documented "classical" failure due to resistive heating and oxidation in air [12]. In fact, we are able to observe such "classical" breakdown when apply either a rapid voltage ramp prior to holding the voltage constant, or a high-amplitude (≈ 1 V), short-duration (≈ 1 ms or less) voltage pulse, such that the CNT locally heats and oxidizes very quickly. An example of the latter is shown in Figure 6. The CNT breaks all occurred left of the center of the gap in roughly the same location on the respective CNT bundles. This observation might be explained by the fact that most of the CNT bundles physically lie on the SiO₂ surface, except near the raised Au contacts. Because the SiO₂-CNT interface may aid in the dissipation of localized heat, the suspended portion of the CNT, surrounded only by air, is likely to become the hottest portion of the CNT.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Despite the limits caused by localized Au migration, the SWCNTs tested are clearly capable of carrying current densities larger than 1 MA/cm² for several hours, if we assume a cross-sectional area equal to the 50 nm electrode height times the 6.4 μ m electrode width. In fact, because only a small portion of the electrode is actually covered by CNTs, and it is unlikely they all equally carry current, this estimate is a lower bound. However, we found that all of the CNTs degrade over time, albeit slowly when applied voltages and corresponding currents are small. The origin of this degradation is not readily

Fig. 5. (a) SEM images of a CNT interconnect after an gold migration event via the slow migration test outlined in Figure 3. Typically migration is more pronounced on the grounded electrode. In this example, voltage was continually increased until open-circuit failure, which led to (b) a seemingly intact but nonconducting failure mode, as highlighted by the dark areas along the CNT bundles.

evident from post-experimental imaging, but qualitatively the current trends (initial increase in current up to a peak value followed by continuous decrease) are similar and appear to be correlated with the input power.

High-input-power experiments qualitatively exhibit these same current trends while also displaying a significant migration of Au electrode material near the CNT-electrode interface. This result suggests that Au migration might occur even at lower input powers, even though the results do not manifest themselves obviously in SEM images. The physical mechanism behind Au migration is scientifically intriguing for a number of reasons. Such current-induced creation of voids and hillocks is reminiscent of classical electromigration but with one important difference. In a classical electromigration event, hillocks are typically formed downstream of voids in the direction of electron flow, as the “electron wind” erodes the conductor metal. Thus, if electromigration were

Fig. 6. (a) Before and (b) after SEM images of CNT interconnects exposed to ≈ 1 V pulse within a very short time frame (< 1 ms). The arrow highlight some of the severed CNT locations which are likely due to localized resistive heating and oxidation.

the sole culprit, one might expect voids to coalesce on the grounded electrode and hillocks to form on the side of the biased electrode. Instead, we find the most pronounced voiding and mounding occurs on the grounded electrode and more importantly in a geometric arrangement contrary to that of typical electromigration theory.

On the other hand, since the largest resistance in most metal-CNT-metal interconnect systems occurs at the CNT-electrode interface, one might suspect that localized heating at these contacts might be lead to thermomigration or even local melting. Although bulk gold melts at temperatures above 1064 °C, recent in situ transmission microscopy work has showed liquid-like behavior in Au thin films at temperatures as low as 166 °C [13]. By applying current densities on the order of 100 MA/cm² through a multiwalled CNT, Asaka et al. [14] demonstrated that the structure of a bulk metal surface can readily melt well below the bulk melting point. If Au is indeed melting locally, the sharp increase in current at the beginning of a test may simply be a result of a much more-efficient and higher-area contact between the CNT and Au electrode. After this initial improvement, further Au recession may then reduce the contact area and lead to less efficient electron injection.

We might expect a heat-induced migration process to depend on the rate at which electrical stress is applied. As indicated in Figure 4, we generally see a higher current peak when a high voltage is applied at a faster rate, which suggests a more catastrophic damage event. In many cases, we observe Au migration more evenly distributed on both electrodes when the applied voltage is increased within a few minutes.

However, Au melting due to localized heating cannot easily explain why Au recession is always more pronounced on the grounded electrode (even when the bias is inverted), since one would expect the local CNT-Au contact resistances on each side to be similar and thus similarly susceptible to resistive heating. This directional dependence upon current suggests that local heating alone may be insufficient to explain Au migration, and that the mechanism may also be a combination of thermomigration and electromigration.

Regardless of the physical origins, these unique reliability issues must be better understood before CNTs can replace Cu as small scale interconnects. The current-induced failure of Au electrodes is particularly alarming, because it suggests that the impressive thermo-electro-mechanical properties of CNTs may be underutilized if the all components of CNT-based interconnects are not carefully designed and manufactured for optimal reliability.

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